

The role of long-range electrostatic interactions and local topology of the hydrogen bond network in the wettability of fully and partially wetted single and multilayer graphene

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Abstract: We report the wetting behaviour of graphitic surface-water interfaces through the calculation of the local stress tensor based on the Irving-Kirkwood-Noll theory using detailed atomistic molecular dynamics simulations. We compare the interfacial properties of fully wetted and partially wetted graphene (*i.e.*, in contact with water on one side and vacuum on the other) and, we observe that the wettability is the result of a fine balance between van der Waals and electrostatic interactions. Such balance is partially perturbed in the case in which graphene is in contact with water on one side and with vacuum on the other. In this scenario, the presence of vacuum and the intrinsic hydrophobic nature of graphene cause water molecules in the proximity of the surface to rearrange building a network of hydrogen bonds dominated by pentagonal rings that allow for enhanced packing and diffusion. Our analyses indicate that the surface tension for the fully wetted graphene layers is ca. 8 mNm^{-1} lower than that of the graphene layers wetted on only one side and this difference only mildly decreases upon adding the graphene layers. We rationalise these observations by investigating how the number of graphene layers affects the topology of the hydrogen bonds network in the proximity of the graphene surface in both systems. We find that water molecules on one side of the graphene layers in the fully wetted system interact with the water molecules on the other side creating a more stable hydrogen bond network. The investigation of the wettability of graphene and graphite is an important aspect in predicting the behaviour of aqueous solutions under nanoconfinements, the permeability of porous materials, the interactions among graphitic surfaces and their dispersion in aqueous environments. Therefore, our results can be applied to interface-related phenomena to better understand the interface where the local energy varies at the nanoscales.

Keywords: Graphene, Water, Wettability, Surface Tension, Local Stress profile, Hydrogen Bond Network.

1. Introduction

The water wettability of carbon surfaces, such as graphene and graphite, has been extensively discussed over the last years due to its broad range of applications, including lubricants¹, desalination membranes², sensors³, protective coating from electrochemical degradation⁴, promotive coating for dropwise condensation⁵.

When a water droplet is in contact with a solid surface, it can either spread on the surface or remain in equilibrium on it forming an angle, θ . This angle, called the equilibrium water contact angle (WCA), can be measured by experiments via, *e.g.*, the sessile drop measurement⁶. In the following discussions we consider “hydrophobic” a surface for which $\theta > 90^\circ$, and “hydrophilic” a surface for which $\theta < 90^\circ$. The primary role in the wetting phenomenon is played by the strength of the substrate-fluid interactions: strengthening the attraction decreases θ and promotes wetting, while weakening the attraction increases θ and promotes drying^{7,8}. Although experimental and theoretical studies have addressed the question about the wetting properties of the graphene layer and multilayers, the actual value of the contact angle of water on an isolated graphene monolayer remains under intense debate⁶. The measurements are indeed challenging because the value of the contact angle can be affected by the nature of the solid surface (roughness and/or chemical heterogeneities, liquid penetration, surface deformation, the number of graphene layers⁹, underlying coated substrate¹⁰), as well as doping induced by substrate¹¹. For these reasons the value of the static contact angle (after the thermodynamic equilibrium is reached) obtained from experiments, may not always correspond to the intrinsic water wettability of pristine graphite and graphene.

Since the early experiments by Fowkes and Harkins in 1940¹², extensive studies have concluded that graphitic surfaces, *i.e.*, highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG), have WCA within the 75-95° range^{12,13-17}. In Table 1 we summarise the results of these studies. Morcos reported a WCA of 84.2° on exfoliated graphite determined by the indirect meniscus height method where the sample was partially immersed in water¹⁸. Adamson and Gast reported advancing WCA of 86° on graphite¹⁹. Raj et al. recently reported advancing WCA on HOPG to be ca. 91°¹⁵. Despite the dominant view that graphite is hydrophobic, a few studies have reported evidence of a much more hydrophilic surface with WCA of 35-65°^{21,28-31}. In 1975, Schrader estimated a WCA of $35 \pm 4^\circ$ of exfoliated

graphite under an ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) environment and proposed that the reported “hydrophobicity” was due to airborne hydrocarbon contamination^{20,22,26}. Additionally, Tadros *et al.* used the captive bubble method and reported advancing WCA of 63-65° on pyrolytic high-density isotropic carbon²⁷. Luna *et al.* also found a WCA of 30° *ca.* on graphite by using scanning force microscopy techniques²⁴. Cao *et al.* found that water on HOPG adsorbs as nanodroplets with WCA of less than 10° under microscopic conditions²⁵. Recently, experimental and theoretical studies have suggested that the contamination due to airborne hydrocarbons increases the hydrophobicity of the graphitic surfaces which are intrinsically hydrophilic^{13, 21, 28–30}.

After the isolation of the first graphene flake by mechanical exfoliation in 2004, researchers have long thought that graphene was hydrophobic. Optical methods and X-RAY reflectivity, as well as molecular dynamics and DFT calculations, revealed a hydrophobic character of graphene as evidenced on the macroscale by a large contact angle, up to 93°, between a water droplet and graphene surface³¹. On the contrary, studies involving WCA measurements coupled with spectroscopy infrared spectroscopy and X-RAY photoelectron investigations showed that intrinsic graphene is mildly hydrophilic but the exposure to volatile hydrocarbons, commonly present in air, lowers its surface energy, making it more hydrophobic³². Recently, Perkin *et al.*³³ have experimentally estimated the surface energy of single layer of graphene $\gamma_{sv} = 115 \pm 4$ mN/m and for few layer 119 ± 3 mN/m with an interfacial energy between water and graphene of $\gamma = 83 \pm 7$ mN/m and a static contact angle of $\theta = 71^\circ$.

It has been also demonstrated that the graphene-water interactions strongly depend on the thickness of the solid substrate, on the layer stacking geometry, on the underlying substrate, and on the substrate-induced doping. Rafiee *et al.* showed that graphene wettability is transparent to the wetting properties of the underlying substrate¹⁰. In this study, it was found that the contact angle between graphene-coated substrates (Si, Au, and Cu) and water only changes slightly compared to the bare substrates. The WCA, however, increased when thicker graphene was overlaid on the substrates so that the coating became more hydrophobic^{9,10}. In other studies, it was also postulated that the contact angle of graphene is dependent on both the liquid-graphene and liquid-substrate interactions, resulting in different degrees of wetting transparency of graphene³⁴. Therefore, graphene is more transparent to wetting on hydrophilic substrates, but opaquer to wetting on hydrophobic substrates. Furthermore, Shih *et al.* demonstrated that graphene is only partially transparent to the wetting properties of the underlying substrate, where the wetting transparency of graphene breaks down when it is placed on superhydrophobic and superhydrophilic substrates³⁵.

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are an invaluable tool to describe the solid-liquid interactions at the atomistic scale and to evaluate both the contact angle and the solid-liquid interface energy. In MD, the WCA the solid-liquid interaction energy is dependent on the choice of force-field parameters^{30,36–39}, the system size⁴⁰, and simulation set up. A recent theoretical work of Malfreyt *et al.* has reported the interfacial tension of the solid-liquid graphene-water interface to be in the range 80-90mN/m, with contact angles in the range 60-70°⁴⁰. Taherian *et al.*, by using thermodynamical approach, evaluated the work of adhesion and the WCA for *n* graphene layers, and have shown a variation in θ from ~ 90 -95° on graphite and of 95-100° on monolayer of graphene¹⁴. Gim *et al.*⁴¹, by using multiscale simulation method of density functional theory in classical explicit solvents (DFT-CES), simulated the surface wettability of a graphene and graphite surface by using SPC/E models and TIP3P-Ew water models. The authors found that the surface wettability is dominantly affected by the strength of the solid-liquid van der Waals interaction and have shown that as the number of graphene layers increases, the van der Waals interactions increase along with the decrease of WCA, *i.e.*, the surface becomes less hydrophobic. More complex systems have been recently simulated by Driskill *et al.*^{42,43}; that simulated the contact angle on graphene sheets using the semi-infinite cylindrical drop model, using the SPC/E water potential. The authors found that the graphene WCA is 10° lower for a system where a water bulk was placed under the graphene than in a system where one side of the graphene was in contact with the vacuum. This work is particularly important when considering real-life scenarios, where graphene is transferred in ambient conditions and water layers are likely to be trapped between the graphene layers and substrate and indicates that the wettability of the surface depends on the nature of the support.

Table 1 Summary of selected experimental results of water contact angles (WCA) and surface energy values of systems with different *n*-layers of graphene in contact with a reservoir of water. (HOPG =highly ordered pyrolytic graphite; RT= Room Temperature, UHV =An Ultrahigh Vacuum)

Ref	Material	n-layers	T [K]	γ_{sl} [mN/m]	γ_{sv} [mN/m]	θ [Degrees]	Technique
Fowkes and Harkins <i>et al</i> 1975 (Ref ⁴⁴ , ¹³⁻¹⁷)	HOPG	---			---	75° -95°	Static WCA
Morcos <i>et al</i> 1970 (Ref ¹⁸)	Pyrolytic Graphite	---	RT		---	84.2	indirect meniscus height method
Schrader <i>et al</i> 1980 (Ref ²²)	Exfoliated Graphite Under UHV Environment	---	RT		---	65	Static WCA by cold finger

Schrader <i>et al</i> 1975 (Ref. ²⁰)	UHV	---	High T	---	35 ± 4	Static WCA
Tadros <i>et al</i> 1974 (Ref ²⁷)	Pyrolytic High- Density Isotropic Carbon	---	326- 328	---	63–65	captive bubble method
Luna <i>et al</i> 1999 (Ref ²⁴)	Graphite				30	scanning force microscopy
Wang <i>et al.</i> 2009 (Ref ¹⁷)	Graphene		RT	54.8	127.0	Static WCA
	Graphite		RT	54.8	98.3	Static WCA
Shin <i>et al</i> , 2010 (Ref ¹⁶)	Graphene And HOPG	1-3 And HOPG	RT		91-92	Static WCA
Cao <i>et al</i> 2011 (Ref ²⁵)	HOPG		RT		<~10°	atomic force microscopy (AFM)
Rafiee <i>et al</i> 2012 (Ref ¹⁰)	Graphene On Cu, Au, Or Si,	1-6			84.1° to 93° (from bulk Cu to graphite)	Static WCA
Raj (Ref ¹⁵) 2013	Graphene and HOPG On SiO ₂ Substrate	1-3, 6		---	91	Static WCA
Kozbial <i>et al.</i> 2014 (Ref. ⁴⁵)	HOPG		278		64	Static WCA
Kozbial <i>et al.</i> 2016 (Ref ⁴⁶)	HOPG (airborn contamination)		278		90	Static WCA
Perkin <i>et al.</i> 2017 (Ref. ³³)	Graphene	1		115 ± 4	71 ± 1	Static WCA
	Graphite	Few Layer	83 ± 7	119 ± 3	70 ± 1	Static WCA

In this work, rather than calculating the WCA from simulations, we estimate the surface tension of fully wetted (*i.e.*, wetted on both sides, Figure 1a) and partially wetted (*i.e.*, in contact with water on one side and vacuum on the other, Figure 1b) graphitic surfaces by spatially resolving the local pressure profile. We model different systems varying the number of graphene layers from 1 to 6. We correlate the resulting surface tension values with the geometry and defects of the network of

hydrogen bonds (HBs) at the interface. We show that the water molecules at the interface with fully wetted graphene and graphite form a more stable hydrogen bond network (HBN) compared to that created by the interfacial water in the partially wetted graphitic systems. These differences translate into a different wettability of the surface. We show that, although the HBN in proximity with graphene surface is different from that of bulk water, the corresponding diffusion of water molecules parallel to the graphene surface is comparable with that of bulk water in most cases, indicating that the perturbations on the HBN is a sensitive metric for interfacial thermodynamic properties and that can be efficiently probed investigating the local stress profile.

2. MODELS AND METHODS

2.1. Simulation details

All MD simulations are performed using GROMACS (v. 2016.3) simulation package⁴⁷ with a simulation time step of 1 fs over an equilibration period of 10 ns. The simulations are performed in the *NVT* ensemble with periodic boundary conditions applied in all directions. The temperature T is fixed at 300 K and controlled via Nose-Hoover thermostat with a time constant of 0.5 ps. Water is described using the TIP4P/2005 model. The LINCS⁴⁸ algorithm is used to maintain holonomic constraints. The local pressure profile is evaluated using the GROMACS-LS (v. 2016.3)^{49,50} software. GROMACS-LS uses a straightforward treatment of constraints within the IKM procedure that remains essentially unchanged in the presence of constraints. It has been suggested that the treatment of constraints in stress calculation algorithms is responsible for reported unphysical nonuniform pressures perpendicular to a bilayer in equilibrium^{49,50}.

The interatomic interactions are modelled using the Lennard-Jones 12-6 potential (cut-off radius 12 Å) and the long-range electrostatic forces are computed using the particle-mesh Ewald (PME) with a grid space of 1.2 Å and a Fourier grid spacing of 0.15. Long-range electrostatic interactions are calculated by means of three-dimensional (3D) Ewald sums as this procedure is fully equivalent to the 2D Ewald procedure^{51,52} for periodic systems in two dimensions. The only requirement that we need to impose is that the cell dimension in the direction perpendicular to the graphene surface, namely the z -axis in our case, is at least five times longer the other dimensions. All the graphene sheets are considered to be rigid, *i.e.*, the carbon atoms are not allowed to move during the simulation. The distance C-C is fixed to 1.418 Å. Water is described using the TIP4P/2005 model, which has been shown to be one of the most accurate models in predicting water surface tension^{51,52}. The

choice of the water model is not a small detail. It has been shown that different water models predict different phase diagrams under confinement⁵³. The TIP4P/2005 model captures the complex phase diagram of water and is robust in quantitatively reproduce the structural, dynamical and thermodynamic properties of water^{54,55}.

The Lennard-Jones parameters for the C-C interaction are $\sigma_{cc}=3.3997$ Å and $\epsilon_{cc}=0.3594$ kJ/mol, which are taken from Ref.⁵⁶. The Lorentz-Berthelot rules are used to produce the parameters of the water-carbon interactions. The Lennard-Jones (LJ) parameters are chosen to reproduce a contact angle of 65°⁵⁶, in agreement with a recent experimental study³³.

All C-C interactions are neglected, all bonded and non-bonded interactions are excluded for pairs of energy groups C-C of graphene. The Lorentz-Berthelot rules are used to produce the parameters of the water-carbon interactions. The carbon atoms of graphene sheets are modelled as neutral particles interacting with the oxygen atoms through the LJ parameters. GROMACS-LS does not take into account the electrostatic contributions computed in reciprocal space, the analysis for atomistic systems simulated with the PME method was performed using Coulomb forces up to a plain cut-off with a radius of 2.0nm, a distance that assures convergence in the stress profile^{49,50}. It is worth noticing that the number of interactions increases cubically with the cut-off radius^{49,50}.

2.2. Surface tension and Evaluation of the local pressures: mechanical route

The surface free energy is derived from its mechanical definition, where the surface tension is obtained from the interfacial stress anisotropy. In their seminal work, Kirkwood and Buff⁵⁷ expressed the component of the stress tensor as a function of the derivative of the intermolecular potential. Such approach has been extensively employed in the computation of fluid-fluid surface tension⁵⁸⁻⁶², while it is more challenging in solid-liquid systems^{56,63}. These challenges arise, for example, from the anisotropy of the solid that leads to a different definition of the surface free energy and the surface stress tensor according to the Shuttleworth relationship⁶⁴, valid only when the interface is free from transverse stresses. As explained above, due to the assumption that in our work the solid surface is rigid, this limitation can be overcome. Moreover, the estimation of the solid-liquid surface tension is strongly affected by finite size effects and by the parameters adopted in the simulations such as, e.g., long range interactions³⁶.

In the Irving-Kirkwood approach^{67,68} the local stress tensor $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ is accessible from interaction forces and velocities of the individual atoms.

For a system with planar symmetry and an isotropic surface, such as a planar graphite layer in contact with water, the tensor $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ can be reduced into the three components: σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} are the parallel vectors to the surface and σ_{zz} is the perpendicular vector. If we consider the stress profile along the perpendicular direction to the surface (z) we define $P_N(z) = -\sigma_{zz}(z)$ which is the normal component of the pressure tensor along this direction, $P_T(z)$ corresponds to the tangential pressure and it is given by $P_T(z) = -\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{xx}(z) + \sigma_{yy}(z))$.

Hence, we can compute the interfacial tension γ through the calculation of the stress profile⁶⁵:

$$\gamma = \int_{-Lz/2}^{Lz/2} (P_N(z) - P_T(z)) dz \quad (1)$$

The details of the method can be found in several publications^{49,50,66,67} including our recent one where we followed the same procedure to calculate the work of adhesion between polyisoprene and graphite⁶².

2.3. Ring statistics

In order to define a ring, we start from a tagged water molecule and recursively traverse the hydrogen bond network (HBN) until we reach the starting point again or we exceed the maximal ring size. As shown in Ref.⁶⁸, this is not the only possible definition. The definition of HB follows the geometrical definition presented in Ref.⁶⁹.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We perform MD simulations for two series of water and graphitic surface systems. In the first system, the graphitic surface is fully immersed in water (Liquid/Solid/Liquid, LSL), while in the second system the reservoir of water is in contact with vacuum (Solid/Liquid/Vapour, SLV) (Figure 1). The systems are reported in Table 2. We investigate the wetting properties as a function of the number n of graphene layers, namely $n=1-3$ and $n=6$ (Figure S1). The reservoir of water is $L_z=100$ Å and it is thick enough to ensure that the density of bulk water is reached, as shown from the density profile in Figure S2.

Table 2. Computational details of the systems simulated in this work. All simulations are performed at $T=300\text{K}$.

	n-layers	$L_x=L_y$ [Å]	$L_z(\text{film})$ [Å]	L_z [Å]	N_{water}	Time [ns]
LSL system (Liquid/Solid/Liquid)	1	51	100	100	8346	100
	2	51	100	100	8302	100
	3	51	100	100	8280	100
	6	51	100	100	8298	100
SLV system (Solid/Liquid/Vapor)	1	51	100	300	8346	100
	2	51	100	300	8302	100
	3	51	100	300	8280	100
	6	51	100	300	8298	100

Figure 1. The snapshots of the two 1-layer graphene systems that we analyse: in panel a), liquid/solid/liquid (LSL) system, a graphene layer interacting with two water reservoirs; in panel b) Solid/Liquid/Vapour (SLV) system, consisting of a reservoir of water molecules in contact with 1 layer and a vacuum. The z -direction is normal to the surface. The surface area is defined by $A=L_x*L_y$ (with $L_x=L_y=51$ Å and $L_z=100$ Å). Red, white and cyan spheres represent oxygen, hydrogen, and carbon atoms, respectively. The simulation box is shown in blue. The panoramic of all analysed systems is reported in Fig. S1.

In order to analyse the structure of water at the solid-liquid interface, the oxygen-oxygen radial 2 D distribution function (*RDF*) in the xy -plane parallel to the surface is analysed for the different systems (see Figure 2). To compute such analysis the simulation box is discretized in slabs of thickness 2 Å along the perpendicular direction to the surface, z . In Figure 2 we report the *RDF*s computed within the slab adjacent to the graphene surface corresponding to the first peak in the density profile, *i.e.*, 3.3 Å from the outer graphene layer (see Figure S2). In Figure 2 we also report the *RDF* computed at

a distance of 65 Å from the graphene surface (magenta), a distance at which water bulk density is recovered.

Figure 2. Water oxygen-oxygen RDF calculated at the interface between water and 1 graphene sheet (black circles and green diamonds) and water and 6 graphene layers (red squares and blue triangles). Magenta star symbols indicate water in the bulk.

We observe that the 2D RDFs computed for water in the bin adjacent to the graphene surfaces (black, red, green, and blue lines) are markedly different from the distribution of bulk water (magenta line). In particular, we observe enhanced first peaks with intensity as high as 4, *i.e.*, much more pronounced than the first peak in bulk water whose intensity reaches ~ 2.5 , and located at $r = 2.75$ Å. This observation is indicative of a local higher packing compared to the bulk and is consistent with the increased water density in the interfacial region (see Figure S2). The RDFs of our systems also show a deeper minimum shifted towards larger values, and a second maximum falling almost in correspondence with the minimum of the second hydration shell in bulk water, in agreement with previous studies^{70–72}. Therefore, the RDFs indicate that the presence of a solid surface has a considerable influence on the structure of the liquid. Such effect is only mildly dependent on the number of graphene layers, *i.e.*, the height of the first maximum shifts from 4.0 Å, for 1 graphene layer, to 4.2 Å for 6 graphene layers. As we will show in the following discussion, such apparent small change has a major effect on the topology of the HBN and on the value of the surface tension.

Figure 3. The lateral component of the stress $\sigma_{xx}(z) = \sigma_{yy}(z)$, between water molecules (TIP4P/2005) at 300 K and for $n=1$ (black star line), 2 (red square line), 3 (blue circle line) and 6 (green line) graphene layers. The normal component $\sigma_{zz}(z) = -P_N(z)$ is constant as reported in SI. In panel a) and b) are reported the curves for LSL system and SLV system respectively. Density plots (filled areas, in arbitrary units on y axis) of water are included for reference.

By computing the local stress profiles, we can correlate these deformations in the local arrangement of water molecules occurring at the interface with the associated excess free energy which gives rise to the interfacial tension. As mentioned above, in this work we follow the Irving-Kirkwood formalism to extract the stress profile from the simulations and evaluate the local pressure profile using the

GROMACS-LS^{49,50} software. In order to compute the profiles of the normal and the tangential stress, we discretize the simulation box into a three-dimensional rectangular grid cell of size $L_{grid}=1 \text{ \AA}$, and we compute the average stress over each cell of the grid along z -direction.

In Figure 3a and 3b, we report the tangential component $\sigma_{xx}(z)$ of the pressure and the corresponding density profiles as a function of the distance from the outer graphene layer of the graphite slab (located at $z=0$) varying the number of graphene layers. The narrow positive peaks in $\sigma_{xx}(z)$ at $z=3.1 \text{ \AA}$ and at $z=6.0 \text{ \AA}$ mark the graphene-water interface, consistent with the maxima in the density profiles. For all the systems, the oscillations of the local stress disappear at $\sim 15 \text{ \AA}$ from the graphite wall, where the density profiles also reach the bulk density.

The normal component of stress $P_N(z) = -\sigma_{zz}(z)$ along z -direction, reported in Figure S3, is nearly constant, in agreement with other studies^{50,73}.

For the LSL system, the first peak in the lateral stress increases upon increasing the number of graphene layers from 1 to 2, and then remains constant upon further increasing in the number of layers up to 6 (see Figure 3a). On the other hand, for the partially wetted graphene system (SLV system) the absence of water on one side of the solid surface affects the height of the first peak of the stress profile and induces a shift in the positions of the subsequent ones (Figure 3b). Such effects have a quantitative counterpart in the topological properties of water HBN, as we will see in the forthcoming discussion. From the stress profiles we can also conclude that the overall balance of forces in the two systems leads to an attractive lateral stress narrowly localised at the interface that increases with the number of layers and with the presence of the second reservoir indicating that in both cases the surface becomes less hydrophobic upon increasing the number of graphene layers.

Figure 4. Profiles of the interfacial tension, $\gamma(z)$, obtained for different system with 1-3 and 6 layers of graphene as a function of z calculated for LSL (panel a) and SLV systems (panel b).

From integrating the difference between the normal and the tangential stress, $(P_N(z) - P_T(z))$ over the z -direction, we obtain the profile of the surface tension, $\gamma(z)$ (Figure 4). For the LSL system (Figure 4a), we report the profile centred at $z=0$, as we have two identical interfaces and the value of solid/liquid surface tension, γ_{sl} , is computed dividing by two the total integral. The profiles present an

oscillatory behaviour at the interfaces that flatten out in the bulk region, where the stress is isotropic. We observe a general trend for all systems as expected, a large narrow and attractive surface tension peak at the interface that tries to minimize the exposed interfacial area with the hydrophobic surface. For the LSL system, the value of $\gamma_{\text{graphene-water}}$ agree well also with a recent experimental study³³ reporting the surface energy of single layer of graphene and water, $\gamma_{\text{graphene-water}}$ to be 83 mN m^{-1} . As we can observe from Figure 3, upon adding graphene layers the surface becomes less hydrophobic and the interfacial surface tension decreases. For the SLV system (Figure 4b), the value of the graphene-water interfacial tension is 98.4 mN/m for a graphene monolayer in agreement with experiments and theoretical work^{33,56} (see Table 3) but, as graphene layers are added, the substrate becomes less hydrophobic and γ_{sl} decreases until it reaches the graphite surface tension value $\gamma_{sF} = 52.2 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ for $n=6$. We also compute the water-vapour surface energy, and we find an average value of $\gamma_{\text{water-vapour}} = 65.4 \pm 3 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$, in very good agreement with the predicted value predicted ($\sim 65.3 \text{ mN/m}$) for the TIP4P/2005 water model⁵².

Using the computed value of the solid-liquid and liquid-vapour surface tensions and the value of graphene/vapour surface energy ($\gamma_{\text{graphene-vapour}} = 115 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$)³³ we can determine the solid-liquid work of adhesion W_{ls} (Tables 3 and 4). The trend of values reported in Tables 3 and 4 are in agreement with previous computational studies^{14,17,31}. Interestingly, we find that the work of adhesion of water on one graphene layer is 70% larger than the work of adhesion of water on graphite. Moreover, for the case of water on supported graphene (Table 4) it is sufficient to add two layers of graphene to reach the graphite/water value, while addition of a third layer is required for the fully wetted graphene system (Table 3).

Table 3. Surface energy values of systems with different n -layers of graphene in contact with a reservoir of water ($L_z^{\text{film}} = 100 \text{ \AA}$) at same $T=300 \text{ K}$ (LSL system). The work of adhesion is computed through the following relationship: $W_{ls} = \gamma_{sv} + \gamma_{lv} - \gamma_{sl}$, where γ_{sv} is the solid-vapor surface tension, γ_{lv} is the liquid-vapor surface tension, and γ_{sl} is the solid-liquid interfacial tension.

n -layers	$L_x=L_y$ [\AA]	$L_z(\text{film})$ [\AA]	γ_{sl} [mN/m]	W_{ls} [mJ/m]
1	50	100	86.1 ± 0.5	100.4 ± 5.0
2	50	100	56.8 ± 0.7	129.7 ± 5.0
3	50	100	48.1 ± 0.9	138.4 ± 5.0
6	50	100	45.2 ± 0.8	141.3 ± 5.0

Table 4 Surface energy values of systems with different n -layers of graphene in contact with a reservoir of water ($L_z^{film} = 100 \text{ \AA}$) and vapor at $T=300 \text{ K}$ (SLV system). The work of adhesion is computed through the following relationship: $W_{ls} = \gamma_{sv} + \gamma_{lv} - \gamma_{sl}$, where γ_{sv} is the solid-vapor surface tension, γ_{lv} is the liquid-vapor surface tension, and γ_{sl} is the solid-liquid interfacial tension.

n -layers	$L_x=L_y$ [\AA]	$L_z(\text{film})$ [\AA]	γ_{sl} [mN/m]	γ_{tot} [mN/m]	γ_{lv} [mN/m]	W_{ls} [mJ/m]
1	50	100	94.8 ± 0.6	158.6 ± 0.6	63.8 ± 0.6	91.7 ± 5.0
2	50	100	65.3 ± 0.5	130.0 ± 0.5	64.7 ± 0.5	121.2 ± 5.0
3	50	100	56.4 ± 1.0	119.8 ± 1.0	63.4 ± 1.0	130.1 ± 5.0
6	50	100	52.2 ± 2.0	122.0 ± 2.0	69.8 ± 2.0	134.3 ± 5.0

From the values reported in Table 3 and 4 we observe that the difference between the surface tension γ_{sl} values for the LSL and for the SLV systems ($\Delta\gamma = \gamma_{sl}(\text{SLV}) - \gamma_{sl}(\text{LSL})$) have a systematic difference which slightly decreases upon increasing the number of graphene layers. In particular, $\Delta\gamma$ decreases from $8.7 \pm 0.6 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ for $n=1$ layer (in agreement with Ref. ⁴²), to 8.5 mN m^{-1} for $n=2$, to 8.3 mN m^{-1} for $n=3$ and to $7 \pm 2 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ for $n=6$ layers. We rationalize this behaviour observing that adding graphene layers translates into increasing the physical separation between the two reservoirs of water, hence decreasing the electrostatic interactions between water molecules on the two sides of the walls and reducing the van der Waals (vdW) interactions between the two reservoirs. In order to understand what the dominant contributions of the intermolecular forces to the value of the surface tension are, we decompose the profile of the total stress tensor into its different contributions (Figure S4). The components include the kinetic and potential stress parts with the latter containing the contributions from pairwise non-bonded (vdW, Coulomb) and bonded interactions.

Figure 5. Profile of electrostatic (panel a) and van der Waals (panel b) components of the tangential stress profile $\sigma_{xx}(z)$ as a function of z for LSL and SLV with n graphene layers ($n=1,3,6$ layers). The different curves refer to distributions for the case with 1 layer (solid black line), 2 layers (the red line with squares), 3 layers (the blue line with

diamonds), and 6 layers (the green line with triangular). The solid lines refer to LSL system and the dashed lines to SLV system.

In Figure 5a and 5b, we report the tangential stress $\sigma_{xx}(z)$ profiles of the vdW and electrostatic contributions for LSL and SLV systems for $n=1-3, 6$ graphene layers. The vdW contribution is due to the interactions between the carbon atoms of the graphene layers and the water molecules and between the water molecules, while the electrostatic contribution is due to interactions between the water molecules only (the carbon atoms in the graphene model we use do not carry any partial charges). For the electrostatic contribution (Figure 5a) we observe only a mild dependency of the height of all the peaks with the number of layers for the LSL (see Figure 5a solid lines) system. This mild dependency is due to the long-range electrostatic interactions between water molecules across the graphene stack. On the other hand, in the SLV system (see Figure 5a dashed lines), the height of the first peak decreases with the number of layers while that of the second peak increases. This behaviour is caused by the absence of the water reservoir in one side in SLV system. Looking at the vdW contributions (Figure 5b), we can see that the trend in the depth and relative position of the first negative peak with the number of layers is similar in both systems. In particular, in the LSL system we converge to the stress value characteristic of graphite (6 layers) at three graphene sheets while for the SLV system the curves converge to the same value at two graphene layers. We also notice that the vdW contributions are responsible for the reduction in the local interfacial pressure (negative values in the corresponding stress) thus contributing to make the surface less hydrophobic.

Figure 5 clearly indicates that long range electrostatic interactions are responsible for the different wetting behaviour of fully and partially wetted graphene and, at least up to a few nm in thickness, graphite. We can quantify such effect upon inspecting the topology of the HBN of water molecules in the proximity of the layer(s) surface and the quality of the network in terms of broken bonds. We probe the topology of the HBN via the ring statistics, a theoretical tool adopted to measure the number of closed loops present in the network of network-forming materials. Ring statistics has been employed to characterise different phases of water as well as the origin of its anomalies^{68,74–78} and to understand the effect of soft confinement in water^{79,80}. In particular, when water is under soft confinement, *i.e.*, confined by a fluctuating biological membrane, the topology of the HBN of bulk water is recovered only at distances up to 25 Å *ca.* from the fluctuating surface, a much larger distance compared to the 10 Å *ca.* distance at which bulk dynamical and density are recovered, but in agreement with the behaviour of other structural properties^{80,81}.

Depending on how rings are built and counted, different physical properties can be probed⁶⁸. Here we adopt the same criterion as in Ref. ⁶⁸. We start from a tagged water molecule and recursively

traverse the HBN until we reach again the starting point, or we exceed the maximal ring size considered, 12 water molecules in our case. Starting from a water molecule, we consider all rings possibly obtained starting from it. In Figure 6a, we report the probability distribution $P(n)$ of having a ring with length n for the LSL system in the closest bin parallel to the graphene surface of width 5 Å where the first two peaks of the pressure profile and density occur. We observe that the HBNs of water at the interface deviates from that of the bulk. In particular, for 1 graphene layer we observe that the distribution is more peaked towards six folded rings (from $P(n)\sim 0.18$ in the bulk to $P(n)\sim 0.20$). It is worth mentioning that cubic and hexagonal ice have a network corresponding to a peaked $P(n)$ over $n=6$ (dotted line in Figures 6a and 6b). Compared to the bulk, the distribution is particularly richer in shorter rings (four- and five-folded rings) with a corresponding depletion of longer rings (from seven-folded to twelve-folded rings). A similar distribution can be observed in the cases with 2 (red line) and 6 (green line) graphene layers. Overall, increasing the number of graphene layers from 2 to 6, we do not see any strong difference in the topology of the HBN. This observation provides a physical explanation for our findings that the minima in the tangential stress do not change upon increasing the number of layers from $n=2$ to $n=6$. In the lower panel, Figure 6b, we report the same distributions computed for the SLV system. We can observe that, in the case of 1 layer (black line), the distribution is remarkably different from the bulk case (blue line), and noticeably different from the same distribution in the LSL system (upper panel). In particular, we now observe a distribution peaked over pentagonal rings instead of hexagonal rings. We ascribe such difference between the LSL and SLV system to the different electrostatic fields that water molecules feel close to the 1 sheet graphene surface: in LSL system the water molecules on one side of the graphene layer interact electrostatically with the water molecules on the other side. Therefore, such mutual interactions help in “stabilising” the HBN that translates into an enhanced hexagonal character. Such electrostatic interactions are, instead, absent in SLV system for which water molecules close to the graphene layer are deprived by the stabilising electrostatic effects of their counterpart. The absence of water molecules on the other side of the graphene layer translates into a different arrangement of the interfacial water molecules and the five-folded peaked ring distribution shown in Figure 6b, lower panel. Upon increasing the number of graphene layers from 2 to 6, we observe a further change in the distribution of rings.

Figure 6. Probability of the hydrogen bond n -member rings, $P(n)$, computed from the water molecules included in bin centred at 2.5 \AA and with a width of 5 \AA . The black line with circular dots represents the distribution for the case with 1 graphene layer, the red line with squares represents the distribution for the case with 2 graphene layers, the green line with diamonds represents the distribution for 6 layers and, finally, the blue line with triangles represents the distribution in bulk water. The upper panel reports the distribution for LSL system, while the lower panel reports the distribution for SLV system. The blue vertical dotted lines represent the limit distribution of a perfect cubic and hexagonal ice.

Upon increasing the distance from the graphene layer, the distributions for both LSL and SLV systems become indistinguishable from one another and from the bulk distribution at distances larger than 10 \AA (see Figure S5).

The marked differences in the topology of the HBN, and in particular, the enhanced pentagonal character of the HBN in the SLV system with 1 graphene layer, suggest differences in the diffusion of water molecules in the proximity of the graphene surface. We then compute the diffusion coefficient, D_{\parallel} (Figure 7), for water molecules along the direction parallel to the surface by using the mean square displacement (*MSD*) as reported in Ref. ^{82,83}. In Figure S6 we report the various profiles for the *MSD*. The parallel diffusion is computed as $D_{\parallel}(\tau) = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle (x_i(t) - x_i(t+\tau))^2 + (y_i(t) - y_i(t+\tau))^2 \rangle}{4\tau P(\tau)}$ where $P(\tau)$ is the survival probability, *i.e.* the probability that a water molecule stays in a water slab during the time interval $t + \tau$. ^{82,83}. Far from the interface, we obtain a value of lateral diffusion coefficient $D_{\parallel} = 0.21 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{ps}$, that corresponds to the bulk value and it is in agreement with other values reported in literature ^{71,84,82}. For the partially wetted system (SLV) with 1 graphene layer, the water lateral diffusion coefficient in the proximity of the surface is markedly higher ($D_{\parallel} = 0.31 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{ps}$) than in bulk. In agreement with previous studies⁷⁴, interfacial water has higher mobility in the direction parallel to the interface than bulk water. This enhanced diffusion is the result of an HBN dominated by pentagonal rings that cause higher local packing compared to the bulk. In the systems with 2 to 6 layers, on the other hand, D_{\parallel} is comparable with the bulk value, although the ring distribution still slightly deviates from that of bulk water. In the fully wetted system (LSL), D_{\parallel} is mildly dependent on the number of graphene sheets, and the D_{\parallel} value is comparable with the bulk one. The similar diffusion is reflected by the comparable network topologies as reported by the ring statistics. These results are also in agreement with the profile of the electrostatic contribution to the stress (Figure 5a): in the system SLV, the first peak decrease upon increasing the number of graphene layers, instead in the LSL system, the first positive peak has comparable height for all system ($n=1-3,6$). These observations indicate that the network topology is an observable more sensitive than diffusion in capturing water's properties ⁸¹ and the local stress profile is an effective analysis tool to capture this effect.

Figure 7. Plot of the lateral diffusion coefficients as function of number of graphene layers for LSL (black dots) and SLV system (red squared). The blue dotted line represents the value of the lateral diffusion coefficient of bulk water, and the blue box the corresponding error.

A good measure of the quality of the network is given by the percentage of coordination defects. We perform a decomposition of the HBs per water molecule into acceptor-(A) and donor-(D) types. We label as A2D2 a water molecule with perfect coordination, *i.e.*, donating two bonds and accepting two bonds. We evaluate the quality of the HBN by computing the ratio of water molecules that have different coordination, *i.e.*, are not in the A2D2 configuration. In particular, we focus our attention on the following coordination configurations: A1D1, A2D1, A1D2, A2D2, and A3D2. Other configurations do not contribute significantly⁸⁰. In Figure 8 we report the percent-wise distribution of coordination defects computed in the same bin in which we have computed the ring statistics shown in Figure 6, centred at 2.5 Å from the surface and width 5 Å. The distribution calculated for the bulk water is strongly peaked towards the A2D2 configuration (~55%), followed by A1D2 (~19%), A2D1 (~11%), A1D1 (~5%), and A3D2 (~3%) coordination defects. This distribution is qualitatively in agreement with the trend in *ab initio* liquid water at ambient conditions examined with different functionals as well as with the distribution in the classical TIP3P water model^{80,85}. For the LSL system, the HBN is characterized by a majority of A2D2 configurations (~35%) followed by A1D2 (~25%), A2D1 (~15%), A1D1 (~12%), and A3D2 (~5%) defects. Increasing the number of graphene layers to 2 (green continuous line) we observe a marked enhancement in the A2D2 configuration up to ~45% with a corresponding depletion of other coordination defects. Upon further increasing the

number of graphene layers up to 6, we observe that the distribution of coordination defects mostly remains unchanged (green line) with respect to the case with 2 graphene layers. This observation agrees with the evidence that the topology of the HBN changes moving from 1 graphene layer to 2 graphene layers, and then it remains mostly unchanged while increasing the number of graphene layers to 6. Upon further increasing the number of layers, the sheets act as a shield leaving the distributions unchanged. As for the SLV system, we observe that the distribution of coordination defects for 1 graphene layer (dashed black line) almost overlap with the same distribution calculated for the LSL system. Upon increasing to 2 layers (dashed red line) the distribution of coordination defects does not change with respect to the case with 1 layer, while it does change increasing the number of graphene layers to 6 (green dashed line). The distribution of bulk water is fully recovered further increasing the distance from the surface, independently on the number of graphene layers. Overall, we observe that the distribution of defects in both systems tends toward the distribution of bulk water as the number of layers increases, in agreement with the trend observed for the topology of the HBN and surface tension. It is worthy to mention, at this point, that the stronger hexagonal character of the HBN shown in Figure 6 is not in contrast with the lowest percentage in A2D2 configurations, because the ring statistics is a measure of the intermediate range order, while coordination defects are strictly a measure of the local coordination.

Figure 8. Percentage-wise decomposition of the intact hydrogen bonds per water molecule into acceptor-(A) and donor-(D) for water in the bins centred at 2.5 Å from the surface and of width 5 Å. The continuous black line with filled circles refers to LSL system with 1 graphene layer, while the continuous red line with filled squares and the continuous green line with filled diamonds refer to the LSL system with 2 and 6 graphene layers, respectively. The dashed black line with empty circles refers to SLV system with 1 graphene layer, while the dashed red line with empty squares and the dashed green line with empty diamonds refer to SLV system with 2 and 6 graphene layers, respectively. The continuous blue line

with filled triangles refers to the distribution in bulk water at the same thermodynamic conditions. The pictorial representations of possible configuration are also reported.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we have employed molecular dynamics simulations for the estimation of interfacial energies and wetting properties of water/graphitic interfaces in two systems, namely a fully wetted one and a system with only one side of the surface in contact with water. For both systems, we have studied the interfacial energies and wetting properties with different number of graphene layers, from $n=1-3$ and $n=6$. We have computed the surface tension of water-vapour and solid-liquid graphitic-water interface from the mechanical route with the Irving-Kirkwood formalism.

In both the fully and partially wetted systems, the profile of the local pressure indicates that water molecules organize in multiple layers. The tangential pressures computed along the graphene surfaces show an oscillatory behaviour up to a distance of ~ 10 Å from the surfaces. We have observed that the first peak continuously increases upon increasing the number of graphene layers in the fully hydrated system, while in the partially hydrated one the intensity of the first peak follows a non-monotonic, noisy behaviour. We ascribe such different profiles to the stabilizing effect that the water molecules on both sides of the graphene in the fully hydrated case exert. Upon increasing the number of graphene layers, we have observed that the surface become less hydrophobic. For all investigated systems, we have observed a general trend, *i.e.*, a large, narrow and attractive stress in correspondence to the interface that tries to minimize the exposed area. Upon adding graphene layers, the surface becomes less and less hydrophobic as there are less unfavourable hydrophobic forces between water and the surface, leading to narrow attractive surface tension. We have then computed the work of adhesion for both systems, establishing a connection between the variation in the work of adhesion and the variation in the water-surface interaction potential.

From the decomposition of the stress profile, we have found that the dominant contributions to the wettability of graphitic surfaces are the electrostatic interactions between the water molecules and vdW interactions water-graphene and between the water molecules. We rationalize this behaviour observing that the addition of graphene layers translates into increasing the physical separation between the two reservoirs of water, hence decreasing the electrostatic interaction between water molecules on the two sides of the walls and “shielding” the vdW interactions between the two reservoirs. We have found that the water-water interaction between molecules across the surface provides an additional stabilization effect to the interfacial water molecules, thereby further increasing the surface wettability.

In order to rationalize our finding, we have inspected the topology and quality of the hydrogen bond

network (HBN) in the proximity of the graphene surface in both systems. In the fully hydrated system, the topology of the HBN, inspected via the ring statistics, changes moving from 1 graphene layer to 2 graphene layers, and then it remains mostly unchanged upon further increasing the number of graphene layers to 6. This observation proves that the presence of water molecules on both sides of the graphene layers stabilizes the network via long electrostatic interactions. Such conclusion is further supported by the profile of the percentage of broken and intact HBs. The distribution of broken and intact HBs varies moving from 1 graphene layer to 2 layers and remains constant with more layers. On the other hand, in the partially hydrated system, we have observed that the topology of the HBN in the proximity of the surface continuously changes upon increasing the number of graphene layers. This behaviour indicates that the absence of water molecules on one side of the surface has a destabilizing effect on the network topology, supporting our previous conclusion. Interestingly, we have found that the topology of the HBN of bulk water is recovered at a shorter distance (~ 10 Å) from the surface compared to the case of water confined by a model phospholipid membrane (~ 25 Å).⁸⁰ Finally, we have correlated the topology of the HBN with the lateral diffusion of water molecules in the proximity of the surface. For the SLV with one graphene layer, where the topology of the HBN is dominated by pentagonal rings, we have found that the lateral diffusion is markedly higher compared with that of bulk water. On the other hand, the lateral diffusion for all other systems is comparable to that of bulk water, although the topology of the HBN is still far from that of bulk water.

Supporting Information

The complete panorama of two series simulated systems (LSL and SLV). The Density profiles for all the studied systems. Profiles of the different contributions of component of the tangential stress tensor of a bulk of water in contact with 1 graphene layer for system LSL and SLV. Distribution of probability of the HB n-member rings computed from structures in different slabs for all systems simulated. The profiles of mean squared displacement of water in the slab closest to surface for both system LSL and SLV.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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